

The Structure and Stereochemistry of D(+)-Pinitol : Application of 2D-NMR Spectroscopy

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The plant *Caesalpinia crista* Linn. (syn. *C. bonducella* Fleming) is known as *Nata* in Bengal. Its use, as mentioned in Ayurvedic literature¹, coupled with its use as one of the components in the antimalarial drug Ayush-64 interested us to reinvestigate the plant. A number of caesalpins² were previously known from this source. Chemical investigation of the plant furnished D(+)-pinitol (**1**) from the methanolic extract of its defatted fruit shells.

Results and Discussion

The methanolic extract of the defatted fruit-shells of *C. crista* on chromatography afforded a compound, characterised as D(+)-pinitol (**1**), C₇H₁₁O₆ (*M*^r 194), m.p. 180° (EtOAc-MeOH), [α]_D + 69° (H₂O). The 300 MHz ¹H nmr of the compound in DMSO-d₆ (after exchange of the hydroxy protons with deuterium) showed a methoxy singlet at δ 3.44, a CH-OMe at δ 3.63 (t, *J* 10 Hz) and five methine protons linked to hydroxyls as overlapped signals at δ 4.3–4.5 (3H, m) and 4.6–4.7 (2H, m). The 75.5 MHz ¹³C nmr exhibited signals at δ 59.72 (OCH₃), 83.85 (CH-OCH₃) and at 70.11, 70.93 (2 carbons), 72.46, 72.63 for five hydroxyl-linked methines. It was necessary to acetylate the compound and examine its spectroscopical properties, particularly nmr, for complete structure clarification.

Acetylation of the compound **1** gave the pentaacetate (**2**), C₁₇H₂₁O₁₁, m.p. 90°, [α]_D + 66° (CHCl₃) which lacked the hydroxyl bands at 3395 and 3300 cm⁻¹ and instead showed bands at 1750 and 1222 cm⁻¹ for acetate in its ir spectrum (KBr). Detailed nmr studies including 2D-experiments of the compound and its pentaacetate decided in favour of structure **1** for the natural product. The complete assignments for the pentaacetate (**2**) are collected in Table 1. A literature search revealed that our compound seemed to be iden-

tical with D(+)-pinitol [lit.³ m.p. 187°, [α]_D + 66° (H₂O)]. The nmr investigations confirmed its structural and stereochemical assignment as 1*R*-methoxy-2*S*,3*S*,4*S*,5*S*,6*R*-pentahydroxycyclohexane (**1**) and further suggested the preferred conformation (**1a**) for the compound and (**2a**) for its acetate in which four of the six oxygenated substituents are equatorial. The 300 MHz ¹H nmr spectrum of D(+)-pinitol pentaacetate (**2**) was recorded and the two-dimensional COSY-45° experiment was performed for assignments of the ring protons.

1. R = H
2. R = Ac

- 1a. R = H
2a. R = Ac

The complete ¹³C and ¹H assignments (Table 1) were achieved from DEPT-135° and two-dimensional ¹³C-¹H correlation experiments. The latter was recorded by the XHCORR pulse sequence with parameters optimised for 1-bond coupling (Fig. 1). The detailed nmr analyses leading to complete assignment has not been reported before.

Experimental

Plant material was purchased from the local market and identified¹. M.p.s. were determined on a Kofler block and are uncorrected. The nmr spectra were recorded on Bruker AM-300 L superconducting magnet spectrometer (¹H at 300.13 MHz, ¹³C at 75.47 MHz) in DMSO-d₆ (for **1**) and in CDCl₃ (for **2**) as solvents.

The air-dried fruit shells (550 g) of *C. crista* was

successively extracted with petrol and ethyl acetate in a Soxhlet apparatus and then with methanol for 20 days in a percolator. The concentrated methanolic extract was chromatographed over silica gel to afford D(+)-pinitol (**1**); (198 mg, 0.36%), C₇H₁₄O₆ (M^r 194), m.p. 180^o, [α]_D + 69^o (H₂O) in the ethyl acetate-methanol (1 : 1) eluates.

Fig. 1 ¹H-¹³C heteronuclear shift correlation by XHCORR sequence
 D(+)-Pinitol pentaacetate (**2**): (+)-Pinitol (100 mg) was acetylated with acetic anhydride (1 ml) and pyridine (0.5 ml) by warming on a water-bath for 1.5 h and worked-up as usual. Chromatography over silica gel furnished the pentaacetate (85 mg, 85%), C₁₇H₂₄O₁₁ (from DEPT and CMR), m.p. 90^o, in the benzene-EtOAc (1 : 1) eluate and was crystallised from petrol-CHCl₃ (3 : 1).

Carbon/proton number	300 MHz ¹ H- ¹³ C chemical shift (δ, multiplicity)	COSY-45 correlation	75.5 MHz ¹³ C- ¹ H chemical shift* (δ)
1	3.60 (t, J 9.7 Hz)	5.30, 5.19	78.45
2	5.10 (dd, J 10.2, 2.8 Hz)	3.60, 5.30	69.25
3	5.30 ^a	—	67.63 ^b
4	5.35	5.17	70.95
5	5.17 (dd, J 10.1, 2.9 Hz)	5.35	70.72
6	5.30 ^a (t, J 10.0 Hz)	—	67.54 ^b
1-OCH ₃	3.44 (s)	—	60.24
Acetate methyl	1.96 2.02, 2.07, 2.14 (two)	—	20.48 20.63 (two), 20.68 (two)
Acetate carbonyls	—	—	169.88, 169.53, 169.47, 169.07, 168.86

* Confirmed by XHCORR experiment (Fig. 1). ^aDistorted multiplets due to second-order effects and obscured by overlap. ^bInterchangeable.

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